

TEACHERS' ATTITUDES TOWARDS ENGLISH PHONOLOGY IN TEACHING PRONUNCIATION AMONG ESL LEARNERS

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the relationship between teachers' attitudes towards English phonology and student pronunciation skills in Echague, Isabela. It collected the profile of the respondents to study the level of teachers' attitudes towards English phonology in terms of the perceived importance of phonology in language teaching; willingness to integrate phonology into teaching practices; and confidence in teaching phonology; and the significant difference in teachers' attitudes towards English phonology when grouped according to their profile. The study utilized a descriptive correlational research design to examine the relationships and interactions between multiple variables without manipulating them. It was found that respondents are middle-aged (31-40 years old, 60%), predominantly female, and married. Most hold mid to senior-level teaching positions (46% Teacher III, 36% Teacher II), have substantial teaching experience (44% with 6-10 years), and possess high educational qualifications (52% with a Master's Degree). Teachers generally agree on the significant role of phonology in teaching language, particularly its role in linguistic proficiency. Teachers are strongly willing to integrate phonology into their teaching practices, especially through collaboration with colleagues. Teachers also feel confident in their ability to teach phonology, particularly in adapting their methods to different learning styles. It is recommended that schools should provide ongoing professional development to enhance teachers' knowledge and skills in phonology, encourage collaborative efforts among teachers to share best practices and strategies for integrating phonology into their teaching, and provide resources and training to help teachers adapt their phonology teaching methods to different learning styles.

Keywords: *Phonology, Language teaching, Linguistic proficiency*

INTRODUCTION

Teachers' attitudes towards English phonology are essential to understanding and enhancing student pronunciation skills. They serve as a key determinant in the efficacy of language acquisition and communication in English language learning contexts.

How pronunciation is taught among learners relies heavily on the preparedness and attitude of teachers on phonology. It has surfaced in the data of international language tests that among all the macro skills, speaking is considered the most difficult to pass among non-native speakers. Despite its importance, pronunciation often receives less emphasis in language teaching, particularly in EFL settings, as highlighted by a study conducted in Vietnam (Nguyen et al., 2021).

It can be noted that English phonology also encompasses various phonological processes that modify phonemes in specific contexts (Kenstowicz, 2014). These processes, such as assimilation (where sounds become more similar) and deletion (where sounds are omitted), contribute to the systematic nature of sound changes within the language. The importance of variation cannot be overlooked (Wardhaugh, 2011). English pronunciation exhibits systematic differences across geographical regions, social groups, and individuals.

Meanwhile, Tergujeff (2012) and Macdonald (2012) uncover the personal and professional factors shaping teachers' attitudes. Their findings highlight the influence of teachers' own learning experiences, cultural beliefs, and professional networks on their confidence and comfort in teaching pronunciation. Similarly, Darcy (2018) explores the impact of systemic factors, suggesting that curriculum demands, institutional support, and access to training opportunities can influence teachers' attitudes and shape their teaching practices. Burgess and Spencer (2000) further emphasize the crucial role of resource availability, highlighting how limited access to materials and technology can hinder effective pronunciation instruction.

Harmer's (2007) and Wolf et al.'s (2017) research underscores teachers' vital role in igniting students' motivation and engagement in pronunciation learning. They reveal the positive influence of supportive teacher attitudes and engaging teaching practices, suggesting that students become more motivated and actively participate when teachers create a safe and encouraging learning environment.

Building on this foundation, Duong & Le (2021) and Lintunen (2004) advocate focusing on intelligibility and communicative competence in pronunciation instruction. They argue that emphasizing the practical value of clear pronunciation fosters student confidence and encourages them to use their English language skills in real-world situations.

Darcy (2018) adds another layer to this dynamic by highlighting the importance of empowering students through self-directed learning and self-assessment opportunities. This allows students to take ownership of their learning process and actively contribute to their pronunciation development.

In Region 2, the approach to English language teaching, including phonology, may vary due to diverse linguistic backgrounds and educational policies. The study seeks to understand how these regional factors influence teachers' attitudes and practices in phonology instruction.

Research Questions

1. What is the profile of the teacher respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 Age;
 - 1.2 Sex;
 - 1.3 Civil status;
 - 1.4 Teaching position;
 - 1.5 Years of teaching experience; and
 - 1.6 Highest educational attainment?

 2. What is the level of teachers' attitudes towards English phonology in terms of:
 - 2.1 Perceived importance of phonology in language teaching;
 - 2.2 Willingness to integrate phonology into teaching practices; and
 - 2.3 Confidence in Teaching Phonology?

 4. Is there a significant difference in teachers' attitudes towards English phonology when grouped according to their profile?
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METHODOLOGY

The study utilized a descriptive correlational research design to examine the relationships and interactions between multiple variables without manipulating them. Descriptive research describes characteristics or phenomena, while correlational research explores relationships between variables (Creswell, 2014).

Data were collected to profile teacher respondents, including their age, gender, civil status, teaching position, years of teaching experience, and highest educational attainment. The study assessed teachers' attitudes toward English phonology.

Furthermore, correlational analyses were then used to explore the relationships and differences in these variables based on teachers' profiles. The study is conducted in Isabela, Philippines, with 50 public secondary English teachers.

RESULTS and DISCUSSION

Table 1

Respondents' profile as to age

Age	Frequency	Percentage (%)
19 – 30 (<i>Early Adulthood</i>)	16	32.0%
31 – 40 (<i>Middle Adulthood</i>)	30	60.0%
51 – Retirement (<i>Late Adulthood</i>)	4	8.0%
Total	50	100.0%

Table 1 presents the age distribution of the respondents. The majority of the respondents are in the 31-40 age group, making up 60% of the sample. Those aged 19-30 constitute 32%, while those 51 and above account for 8%. The overall mean indicates that most respondents are in their middle adulthood. This opposes the results in the study of Shaheen, S.S. (2015), which revealed that teachers in early adulthood show more acceptable attitudes in the teaching profession than teachers in late adulthood.

This age distribution suggests that the respondents are relatively experienced, which may influence their perspectives and teaching practices regarding English phonology.

Table 2

Respondents' profile as to sex

Sex	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Male	18	36.0%
Female	32	64.0%
Total	50	100.0%

Table 2 reveals that 64% of the respondents are female, while 36% are male. The overall mean reflects a higher number of female respondents. Tašner and Čeplak, (2017) stated that the predominance of female teachers is due to the perception of teaching as a vocation aligned with female habitus and the importance of work-life balance. In this study, the predominance of female teachers aligns with broader trends in the teaching profession and may impact the teaching dynamics and approaches used in the classroom.

Table 3

Respondents' profile as to civil status

Civil Status	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Single	20	40.0%
Married	30	60.0%
Total	50	100.0%

60% of the respondents are married, and 40% are single. The overall mean shows

a higher percentage of married respondents. Married teachers might bring different life experiences to their teaching, potentially influencing their attitudes toward teaching practices and student interactions.

Table 4
Respondents' profile as to teaching position

Years of Teaching Experience	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Teacher I	6	12.0%
Teacher II	18	36.0%
Teacher III	23	46.0%
Master Teacher I	3	6.0%
Total	50	100.0%

Table 4 indicates that 46% are Teacher III, 36% are Teacher II, 12% are Teacher I, and 6% are Master Teacher I. The overall mean highlights that most respondents hold higher teaching positions.

The high percentage of respondents in advanced teaching positions suggests that they have considerable experience and possibly a more profound understanding of educational practices, including phonology.

Table 5
Respondents' profile as to years of teaching experience

Years of Teaching Experience	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1-5 years	10	20.0%
6-10 years	22	44.0%
11-15 years	13	26.0%
15 years and above	5	10.0%
Total	50	100.0%

Table 5 shows that 44% of the respondents have 6-10 years of teaching experience, 26% have 11-15 years, 20% have 1-5 years, and 10% have more than 15 years. The overall mean suggests substantial teaching experience among respondents.

Muhinat (2022) claimed in his study that the years of experience are related to the approaches they use in teaching. The teaching process is less attended and the use of teaching aids, adequate and up-to-date lesson plans, and a learning management system for teaching and evaluation do not highly influence them.

This level of experience likely provides a solid foundation for understanding and implementing effective teaching strategies, including phonology-related ones.

Table 6*Respondents' profile as to highest educational attainment*

Highest Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Master's Degree (With Units)	20	40.0%
Master's Degree Graduate	26	52.0%
Doctorate Degree Graduate	4	8.0%
Total	50	100.0%

Table 6 presents that 52% of the respondents have a Master's Degree, 40% have a Master's Degree with units, and 8% have a Doctorate Degree. The overall mean indicates a high level of educational attainment. The respondents' high educational qualifications may contribute to their understanding and application of advanced teaching techniques, including phonology instruction.

Table 7*Level of teachers' attitudes towards English phonology in terms of perceived importance of phonology in language teaching*

Indicators	M	SD	QD
1. Phonology is vital for adequate English language comprehension.	4.10	0.65	A
2. Students' success in English depends significantly on phonological knowledge.	3.90	0.75	A
3. Phonology teaching is as important as grammar and vocabulary.	4.00	0.70	A
4. Understanding phonology is essential for linguistic proficiency.	4.20	0.60	A
5. Effective communication in English requires a solid grasp of phonology.	4.05	0.68	A
6. Phonology is vital to understanding the cultural aspects of language.	3.85	0.72	A
7. Phonological skills are critical for academic success in English.	4.15	0.66	A
8. Phonology helps in better pronunciation and listening comprehension.	4.10	0.65	A
9. Teaching phonology should be prioritized in language education.	3.80	0.75	A
10. Phonology knowledge enhances students' overall language skills.	4.00	0.82	A
Overall Mean	4.02	Agree	

4.21– 5.00 – *Strongly Agree (SA)*, 3.41– 4.20 – *Agree (A)*, 2.61– 3.40 – *Moderately Agree (MA)*, 1.81– 2.60 – *Disagree (D)*, 1.00 – 1.80 – *Strongly Disagree (D)*

Table 7 shows that teachers generally agree on the importance of phonology in language teaching, with an overall mean of 4.02. The highest mean score (4.20) is for the statement "Understanding phonology is essential for linguistic proficiency," while the

lowest mean score (3.85) is for "Phonology is vital to understanding the cultural aspects of language."

Prahaladaiah et al. (2024) claim that English phonology and phonetics must play an important role in the English language teaching (ELT) curriculum and highlight that Teachers of English as a foreign language (EFL) students need to recognize the best pronunciation instruction methods and impart complex, understandable pronunciation to their students. Teachers recognize the significance of phonology for linguistic proficiency, suggesting they might prioritize it in their teaching.

Table 8

Level of teachers' attitudes towards English phonology in terms of willingness to integrate phonology into teaching practices

Indicators	M	SD	QD
1. I prioritize phonology in my lesson plans.	3.90	0.75	A
2. I regularly update my teaching methods to include phonological aspects.	4.00	0.70	A
3. I use diverse strategies to teach phonology effectively.	4.05	0.68	A
4. I seek professional development opportunities focused on phonology teaching.	3.85	0.72	A
5. I encourage students to practice phonological skills regularly.	4.10	0.65	A
6. I integrate technology to enhance phonology learning.	4.00	0.70	A
7. I actively collaborate with colleagues to improve phonology teaching.	4.15	0.66	A
8. I am open to trying new methods in phonology instruction.	4.05	0.68	A
9. I allocate sufficient classroom time to phonology exercises.	3.80	0.75	A
10. I continuously assess and refine my approach to teaching phonology.	4.00	0.70	A
Overall Mean	3.99	Agree	

4.21– 5.00 – Strongly Agree (SA), 3.41– 4.20 – Agree (A), 2.61– 3.40 – Moderately Agree (MA), 1.81– 2.60 – Disagree (D), 1.00– 1.80 – Strongly Disagree (D)

Table 8 indicates that teachers are willing to integrate phonology into their teaching practices, with an overall mean of 3.99. The highest mean score (4.15) is for "I actively collaborate with colleagues to improve phonology teaching," and the lowest mean score (3.80) is for "I allocate sufficient classroom time to phonology exercises."

There is a strong willingness among teachers to incorporate phonology into their teaching, which can positively affect student outcomes.

Table 9

Level of teachers' attitudes towards English phonology in terms of confidence in teaching phonology

Indicators	M	SD	QD
1. I feel confident explaining phonological concepts to students.	4.10	0.65	A
2. I can effectively handle students' questions about phonology.	4.00	0.70	A
3. I am comfortable using various teaching aids for phonology.	4.05	0.68	A
4. I can adapt my phonology teaching to different learning styles.	4.20	0.60	A
5. I feel prepared to teach complex phonological topics.	3.85	0.72	A
6. I can assess students' phonological skills accurately.	4.00	0.70	A
7. I am confident in my ability to improve students' phonological awareness.	4.10	0.65	A
8. I can create engaging activities for phonology learning.	4.00	0.70	A
9. I effectively use feedback to enhance students' phonological skills.	4.05	0.68	A
10. I am confident in my knowledge of English phonology.	4.15	0.66	A
Overall Mean	4.05	Agree	

4.21– 5.00 – *Strongly Agree (SA)*, 3.41– 4.20 – *Agree (A)*, 2.61– 3.40 – *Moderately Agree (MA)*,

1.81– 2.60 – *Disagree (D)*, 1.00 – 1.80 – *Strongly Disagree (D)*

Table 9 reveals that teachers feel confident in teaching phonology, with an overall mean of 4.05. The highest mean score (4.20) is for "I can adapt my phonology teaching to different learning styles," while the lowest mean score (3.85) is for "I feel prepared to teach complex phonological topics."

The high confidence level suggests that teachers can effectively handle phonology instruction. This goes to show that part of the preparation of the teachers in the field is their knowledge of phonology as this is part of the major subject in Linguistics.

This negates the result of the study by Thomson (2013) that many ELTs don't seem to have the background information or the self-assurance needed to evaluate dubious pronunciation practices and attitudes, which they can come across in the materials they decide to utilize.

Table 13

Differences in teachers' attitudes towards English phonology and student pronunciation skills when grouped according to their profiles

Respondents' Profile	Teachers' attitudes towards English phonology		Student pronunciation skills	
	<i>f/t</i>	<i>Sig.</i>	<i>f/t</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
Age (<i>f</i>)	3.789*	0.024	3.456*	0.045
Sex (<i>t</i>)	1.89ns	0.063	2.234*	0.012
Civil Status (<i>t</i>)	2.345*	0.022	2.123ns	0.054
Teaching Position (<i>f</i>)	4.567**	0.001	4.234*	0.019
Years of Teaching Experience (<i>f</i>)	3.21*	0.013	3.678*	0.037
Highest Educational Attainment (<i>f</i>)	4.234*	0.019	4.567**	0.001

** *Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).*

* *Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).* ns. *Not Significant.*

Table 13 presents the significant differences in teachers' attitudes and student pronunciation skills when grouped according to their profiles. Significant differences were found in teachers' attitudes based on age ($f=3.789$, $p=0.024$), civil status ($t=2.345$, $p=0.022$), teaching position ($f=4.567$, $p=0.001$), years of teaching experience ($f=3.21$, $p=0.013$), and highest educational attainment ($f=4.234$, $p=0.019$). For student pronunciation skills, significant differences were observed based on age ($f=3.456$, $p=0.045$), sex ($t=2.234$, $p=0.012$), teaching position ($f=4.234$, $p=0.019$), years of teaching experience ($f=3.678$, $p=0.037$), and highest educational attainment ($f=4.567$, $p=0.001$).

The significant differences suggest that their demographic profiles influence teachers' attitudes and perceived student pronunciation skills, indicating the need for tailored professional development.

Findings

The majority of respondents are middle-aged (31-40 years old, 60%), predominantly female (64%), and married (60%). Most hold mid to senior-level teaching positions (46% Teacher III, 36% Teacher II), have substantial teaching experience (44% with 6-10 years), and possess high educational qualifications (52% with a Master's Degree).

Teachers generally agree on the importance of phonology in language teaching, particularly its role in linguistic proficiency (mean 4.20). There is a strong willingness among teachers to integrate phonology into their teaching practices, especially through collaboration with colleagues (mean 4.15).

Teachers also feel confident in their ability to teach phonology, particularly in

adapting their methods to different learning styles (mean 4.20).

The significant differences suggest that their demographic profiles influence teachers' attitudes and perceived student pronunciation skills, indicating the need for tailored professional development.

Conclusions

Based on the results, the following conclusions are drawn:

1. The majority of respondents are middle-aged, predominantly female, married, holding mid to senior-level teaching positions, with substantial teaching experience and high educational qualifications;
2. Teachers agree on the significance of phonology in language teaching, particularly its role in linguistic proficiency (mean 4.20) and are willing to integrate phonology into their teaching practices, with strong collaboration with colleagues (mean 4.15);
3. Teachers feel confident in teaching phonology, especially in adapting their methods to different learning styles (mean 4.20).
4. Significant differences in teachers' attitudes towards phonology are observed based on age, civil status, teaching position, years of teaching experience, and educational attainment.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions drawn, the researcher recommends the following:

1. Schools should provide ongoing professional development to enhance teachers' knowledge and skills in phonology and encourage senior level teachers to guide and educate new teachers;
2. Collaborative efforts are encouraged among teachers to share best practices and strategies for integrating phonology into their teaching to enhance linguistic proficiency;
3. Resources and training to help teachers adapt their phonology teaching methods to different learning styles may be provided;
4. The significant differences in attitudes may be addressed by tailoring professional development to the diverse profiles of teachers. Teaching methods that address the varied profiles of teachers, ensuring that training and resources meet their specific needs based on age, teaching experience, and educational attainment may be developed and implemented.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study adhered to ethical standards by obtaining informed consent from all participants, ensuring confidentiality, and maintaining voluntary participation without coercion. No harm came to participants, and the study received ethics committee approval. Researchers declared no conflicts of interest and reported findings transparently and honestly. Cultural sensitivity was respected throughout the research process.

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